

AN OVERVIEW OF THE WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES IN THE ZIZ BASIN, SOUTHEAST OF MOROCCO

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The Ziz Basin is within an arid climate, with limited water availability, and growing demand for water resources. As a result, sustainable management of water resources becomes imperative to ensure the well-being of both the environment and the local communities. Surface and groundwater are under increasing pressure due to low annual rainfall (45 to 275 mm), decreasing stream flow and increasing pumping due to agricultural activities. In this work, we highlight the impact of increasing irrigation water demand on the water balance of the Ziz basin, based on multivariate statistical analysis combined with GIS techniques of a dataset from (2009 to 2021). Results show that crop water demand exceeds supply in the entire study area. Crop water requirements in the middle Ziz valley are better covered than in the Tafilalet plain. The needs satisfaction rates are 50 and 40%, respectively in the perimeters of the middle Ziz valley and the Tafilalet plain with high interannual variability. In 2018-2019, considered a dry year, the coverage rates are very low (between 22 and 15%). Water consumption for irrigation purposes in the Ziz Basin has increased, especially in recent years with the installation of large palm and watermelon farms in the region. On the other hand, an observation of the stream flows on 6 gauging stations shows low values, oscillating between 0.75 and 3.30 m³/s in medians on a series between 1954 and 2014. Faced with these realities, the situation is becoming increasingly critical and threatens the availability of water resources in the Ziz basin. Therefore, water management measures such as the use of modern irrigation methods, the adaptation of crops, and the use of unconventional water are encouraged for resource sustainability in this fragile ecosystem.

Keywords: Water availability; irrigation water; crops adaptation; resource sustainability; Tafilalet plain; middle Ziz valley.

Acknowledgment. This study is supported by project EWALD which has received funding from the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027), Grant Agreement No. ID 101086250